

Debjit Ghosh <debjitghosh15@gmail.com>

Request for translations of Bladder Cancer Index (BCI) in Indian languages Hindi & Bengali for conducting a scientific research

Drew Bennett <andbenne@umich.edu>

Tue, Dec 17, 2024 at 12:52 AM

To: Debjit Ghosh <debjitghosh15@gmail.com>

Cc: "Jtwei@umich.edu" <Jtwei@umich.edu>, "Wei, John (John)" <jtwei@med.umich.edu>

HI Debjit,

The license can be found here: <https://available-inventions.umich.edu/product/bladder-cancer-index-bci>

Regards,

Drew

Drew Bennett

Director - Software, Content Licensing and Research Partnerships

Innovation Partnerships

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"Ask not for victory, ask only for courage. In your pursuit, you bring honor to yourself. But more important, you bring honor to us all."

— Ancient Greek saying, Recited at Annual Runners' Briefing, [Western States Endurance Run](#).

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